

Shallow Depth P-wave Velocity Profiling Using Seismic Interferometry: The CORSSA Site

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Abstract

We apply the method of seismic interferometry by deconvolution to analyze vertical accelerometer array data from the CORSSA site in Greece and determine P-wave velocities (V_P) at shallow depths. We show that in the case of the CORSSA site, the method is able to overcome the challenges of resolving the much faster P-wave travel times and provide statistically robust mean velocity values for different depth ranges. Thus, we propose a V_P velocity model for the studied site to complement the previously proposed V_S models. We also compare the interferometry inferred $V_P V_S$ values with independent results and find them to be realistic and consistent with empirical relationships based on rich data sets from different parts of the world. Within the nearly 10 years that the studied dataset spans, we observe a significant temporal variation of V_P , mostly in the shallower depth ranges studied, which appears to be longer in duration than the seasonal variation previously reported for V_S at this site. However, the lack of temporal continuity in our dataset does not allow a detailed analysis of this variation.

Background and objectives

Changes in the ratio of P-wave to S-wave velocity, V_P/V_S , in soft sediments often reveal variations in fluid content, sediment compaction, material composition, and stress conditions. Monitoring these changes is critical for both geotechnical and geophysical applications. Historically, the method of seismic interferometry by deconvolution has been applied to horizontal recordings of vertical accelerometer array data sets to monitor temporal variations of V_S at shallow depths (e.g., Nakata and Snieder, 2011; Chandra et al., 2016; Gueguen, 2016; Roumelioti et al., 2020, Qin et al., 2022). The vertical component is usually not exploited in the specific method, primarily because the much faster travel times of P-waves are difficult to resolve.

The CORSSA vertical accelerometer array (e.g., Kassaras et al., 2016) was installed in the coastal area of the city of Aigio (northern Peloponnese, western Gulf of Corinth) a few years after the catastrophic 1995 M6.5 Aigio earthquake. The primary goal of this infrastructure was to collect strong motion records to be used in studies of site effects and soil response. To understand the changes in the seismic wavefield as it propagates from the bedrock to the ground surface, four stations were installed inside boreholes at different depths (14, 31, 57 and 178 m) and one station was installed on the surface inside a lightweight protective structure. The infrastructure operated in trigger mode for several years, although with several interruptions due to technical problems, and its data for the period 2002-2012 have been organized and published as a database (<http://corssa.gr/>; Kassaras et al., 2016).

The CORSSA dataset has been analyzed by seismic interferometry by deconvolution with respect to the horizontal recordings and associated V_S (Roumelioti et al., 2018), revealing a seasonal variation of V_S in shallow layers that decreases with depth and becomes undetectable below ~30m. In this work, we extend the analysis to the vertical components of the earthquake records in the CORSSA database, with the aim of determining the V_P profile for the CORSSA site and investigating the V_P values with respect to previously published V_S in terms of their ratio, V_P/V_S , and its change with depth.

Methods and Data

Seismic interferometry by deconvolution on an array of sensors comprises the division of the spectral representation of one trace at one receiver by that of another. Assuming that the distance between a specific earthquake source and the array is many times larger than the array inter-station distances, the spectral division is expected to remove any source-specific imprints and common path propagation effects, yielding the transfer function of the medium between the two involved stations, which resembles a pulse signal. This transfer function is the inverse Fourier transform of:

$$D_{j-i}(\omega) = \frac{A_j(\omega)A_i^*(\omega)}{|A_i(\omega)|^2 + \varepsilon} \quad (1)$$

where $A_j(\omega)$ and $A_i(\omega)$ represent the Fourier transforms of the recordings at the j -th and i -th (reference) receivers, respectively, and ε the water-level parameter, introduced to stabilize the deconvolution at very low denominator values (Clayton and Wiggins, 1976). By measuring the travel times of the resulting pulses and knowing the exact distances between stations in the array, it is possible to compute wave velocities in the between the two stations propagating medium.

For this study, the seismic interferometry by deconvolution was applied to the vertical components of recordings from four CORSSA borehole stations, using the surface station as a reference. In total, we analyzed records of 709 earthquakes at each

station. Some characteristics of the dataset, such as the distribution of magnitudes (local magnitude, M_L) in magnitude bins, the distribution of magnitude with epicentral distance, and the distribution of peak ground acceleration (PGA) with distance, are shown graphically in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Brief description of the processed dataset: a) Distribution of earthquake records in the dataset in magnitude (M_L) bins, b) M_L occurrences and c) PGA (east-west component of the surface CORSSA station) with respect to the epicentral distance of the earthquakes from the CORSSA site.

We set $\epsilon=10\%$ and resampled the inverse Fourier transform of $D_{j-i}(\omega)D_{i-j}(\omega)$ with a step 100 times smaller than the original. In this way, we artificially densified the pulse-like transfer functions to improve the accuracy of the picking of the travel time of the pulse (e.g., Roumelioti et al., 2020; Qin et al., 2023). Figure 2 shows a sample output from the application of the described method to the vertical recordings of a M_L 3.5 earthquake at 14 km distance. The subplots show the results of the interferometry at different depth intervals and include an upward propagating pulse. We use the top of this pulse as a characteristic point to follow its propagation and measure its travel times from one sensor depth to the other. At the 14m subplot in Figure 2, two pulses appear, one on the negative side of the time axis and one on its positive side. This means that there is significant wave energy that has been reflected at the surface and propagated downward, but it does not affect our results, which are based solely on time measurements on the negative side. In recordings richer in low frequencies, or as V_p increases, the two pulses may move closer together and become inseparable, making it impossible to measure V_p .

Figure 2. Example output of the interferometry by deconvolution on the vertical components of a record (29/12/2011, 15:19UTM, M_L 3.5, R14km) at the CORSSA site. Each subplot shows the deconvolution of a waveform at the depth marked on the top right with respect to the waveform at the surface. A propagating pulse appears on the negative side of the x-axis and its top is marked (red dot) as a characteristic point to measure time differences (i.e., travel times).

V_p from seismic interferometry by deconvolution

We have applied seismic interferometry by deconvolution to resolve P-wave velocities in the depth intervals 0-14 m, 0-31 m, 0-57 m, 0-178 m, 14-31 m, 31-57 m, and 57-178 m. As noted above, there are inherent difficulties in applying the method to the much faster P-waves. The first is the sampling rate commonly used for ground acceleration monitoring, which is low for resolving very small changes in the propagation time of the impulse response of soft soils. In our case (sampling rate of 200 s/s), we limit this restriction to some extent by resampling the interferometric result at a higher rate, allowing a more accurate measurement of the travel times. The second major difficulty is the very high velocities of the P-waves, even in soft sediments, which in combination with the often small distances between the stations result

in extremely short travel times that cannot be resolved. A third difficulty is that the wavelengths of interest change as we attempt to define velocities at different depth intervals, and not all recordings have the necessary frequency content to provide an unambiguous time reading. As a result, the efficiency of the method at a particular location and depth interval may not always be known a priori, but only through trial and error. Furthermore, even if the method is successful but V_p increases with time, it may fail above a certain level of increase.

For all of the above reasons, in our application at the CORSSA site although we had many stable results, we also had numerous “outliers”, which we define in the following. To isolate and work with the most populated concentrations of resulting V_p values, we applied a two-step interquartile range (IQR) outlier removal. First, we removed V_p values that were outside 3 times the IQR (Q3-Q1) of the overall distribution. These “extreme” outliers were also manually checked and were found to be related to poor quality waveforms or to the events with the richest low-frequency signal, resulting in broad pulses with an almost flat top (i.e., the area where we usually expect a sharp peak to be used for travel time measurement). In the second step, we performed a standard removal of values outside 1.5 times the IQR. The procedure is shown graphically in Figure 3 for the example case of the 0-14m depth interval. The IQR, i.e., the area where 75% of the computed values are concentrated, is shown in purple and the lighter color marks the 1.5×IQR area. Everything that falls within these two areas is included in the subsequent analysis, and values outside these areas are considered outliers. Figure 3 also marks the mean of the finally considered values ± 1 standard deviation (s.d.).

Figure 3. Graphical description of the outlier removal procedure for the example case of V_p estimates for the depth interval 0-14m. Gray points, lying beyond 1.5 times the interquartile range (IQR) (orange shaded area), are considered as outliers and are not being used in the estimate of the mean V_p value.

The results of the interferometry by deconvolution for all depth intervals examined are summarized in Table 1. More specifically, Table 1 lists percentage of final data points and outliers with respect to the initial dataset of 709 earthquake records for each depth interval, the mean $V_p \pm 1$ s.d. and the corresponding information for the two horizontal components (from Roumelioti et al., 2018), east-west (V_{se}) and north-south (V_{sn}), for comparison. The agreement of the results of the two V_s is remarkable, as well as the amount of data finally considered for V_p despite the difficulties mentioned above. The depth interval with the largest number of outliers, for both V_p and V_s computations is the 0-178m interval. This is a rather unsurprising result considering the very weak character of most of the waveforms in the dataset (Kassaras et al., 2016) (Figure 1c). An interesting finding was the high mean V_p in the 14-31m depth interval, quite higher than the underlying examined “layer”, most likely indicating an increased presence of groundwater.

Table 1. Mean V_p and V_p/V_s values inferred from interferometry for the CORSSA site and percentages of determined values and outliers with respect to the starting dataset. Depth intervals are defined by the downhole sensors’ installation depths. V_s values for the two horizontal components of Roumelioti et al. (2018) are included for comparison.

Depth Interval (m)	Data/Outliers (%) for V_p	V_p (± 1 s.d.) (m/sec)	Data/Outliers (%) for V_{se}	V_{se} (± 1 s.d.) (m/sec)	Data/Outliers (%) for V_{sn}	V_{sn} (± 1 s.d.) (m/sec)	V_p/V_{se}	V_p/V_{sn}
0-14	76/24	813 (135)	97/3	208 (7)	97/3	214 (8)	3.9	3.8
0-31	93/7	1135 (107)	99/1	240 (6)	98/2	240 (6)	4.7	4.7
0-57	77/23	1224 (96)	96/4	268 (4)	94/6	268 (4)	4.6	4.6
0-178	67/33	1710 (59)	63/37	430 (4)	61/39	424 (15)	4.0	4.0
14-31	76/24	1754 (233)	93/7	277 (7)	86/14	271 (11)	6.3	6.5
31-57	81/19	1382 (46)	91/9	308 (3)	93/7	314 (4)	4.5	4.4
57-178	87/13	2140 (32)	71/29	602 (5)	60/40	583 (11)	3.6	3.7

Figures 4 and 5 show the results graphically, Figure 4 for interferometry results with respect to the surface station and Figure 5 for pairs where both stations were in boreholes. Each row of the subplots corresponds to a different depth interval (i.e., station pair in the interferometry), while the columns from left to right include: the V_p values derived in this study, the V_{se} and V_{sn} values computed by Roumelioti et al. (2018) using the same method. In all subplots, the mean velocity ± 1 s.d. (i.e., the values included in Table 1) is also marked. Although our dataset is not continuous in time, it is clear that there is a temporal variation in both V_p and V_s values that increases in amplitude with depth. Although the left column in Figure 4 may suggest some seasonal variation, it is certainly not as clear as for V_s , and the temporal discontinuity of the dataset examined, as well as the variability of V_p make any identification even more difficult. It is possible that the temporal variation of V_p is longer in period than an expected seasonal one. This can be seen very clearly in the upper left subplot of Figure 4, where V_p values in 2003-2004 are mostly clustered around 700m/s, whereas in 2006-2008 they are around 800m/s. Reasons for such slower changes could be, for example, multi-year changes in groundwater, or sudden compaction of sediments after shaking caused even by relatively distant strong earthquakes.

Figure 4. Velocity variation with time for depth intervals noted at the top of each subplot (0-14m, 0-31m, 0-57m, 0-178m from top to bottom). The left column contains the V_p values, the middle the V_s in the east-west component (V_{se}) and the right column the V_s in the north-south component (V_{sn}). V_s values are taken from Roumelioti et al. (2018).

Figure 5. As in Figure 5, but for the intermediate depth intervals (from top to bottom) of 14-31m, 31-57m, and 57-178m. V_p profile at the CORSSA site

The mean VP values derived for the depth intervals 0-14m, 14-31m, 31-57m and 57-178m are plotted in Figure 6 in the form of a velocity profile, along with previously proposed VS profiles (CORSSA, 2002; Roumelioti et al., 2018). Although the applied method provides well-constrained mean VP values directly at the site and from actual ground motion data, a shortcoming is that the interferometric “layer” thicknesses in Figure 6 have no physical or geological meaning and are defined by the depths of the sensors in the accelerometer array.

Figure 6. Seismic wave velocity profiles at CORSSA. The V_p profile is a result of this study and “layers” thicknesses are enforced by the depths of the borehole array sensors. The V_s profiles are from Roumelioti et al. (2018) and include the information from the European project “CORSEIS” (2002) as originally provided and resampled at the depth intervals of the CORSSA array.

V_p/V_s ratio

The last two columns in Table 1 show the V_p/V_s using the mean velocity values for each depth interval examined. The results using the mean V_s values in the two horizontal components show insignificant differences. V_p/V_s has values <4 in the shallowest (0-14m) and deepest (57-178m) depth ranges and well >4 in the 14-31m and 31-57m intervals. Figure 6 shows how these values compare to previously published V_p - V_s relations. We chose to compare the CORSSA values to the empirical relation of Brocher (2005), who has incorporated many northern California profiles that are more representative of younger tectonic terranes such as the one examined in this study. We also compare our values with two relations proposed in a more recent study by Nagashima and Kawase (2021), which is based on a very large number of KiK-net and K-NET station sites in Japan. Nagashima and Kawase (2021) found an abrupt increase in V_p around 4m depth and attributed it to the transition from unsaturated to saturated soil formations. As a result, they proposed two different V_p - V_s relationships. The CORSSA values for the three deepest ranges investigated compare well with the Brocher (2005) relation and the saturated soil version of Nagashima and Kawase (2021). The 0-14m appears to be more compatible with the unsaturated version of the Nagashima and Kawase (2021) relationship, suggesting that the top 14m at CORSSA is mostly unsaturated. This is also supported by the absolute value of the mean V_p for this layer, ~ 800 m/s, which is much lower than the speed of P-waves in water (1200 to >1400 m/s, also depending on the salinity).

Figure 6. Mean V_p versus mean V_s for the examined depth intervals at the CORSSA site. Blue straight lines mark the V_p , V_s relation for Poisson's ratios (ν) of 0.45-0.49. Previously published pertinent relations are also shown for comparison; black curve for Brocher (2005) and red dashed curves for Nagashima and Kawase (2021; N&H) for saturated and unsaturated soils.

Conclusions/Discussion

We applied the method of seismic interferometry by deconvolution to the vertical components of a dataset of 709 earthquake records at the CORSSA borehole array. We examined the four borehole stations of the array (at depths of 14, 31, 57 and 178m) with respect to the surface station, as well as station pairs at 14-31m, 31-57m, and 57-178m, and computed V_p velocities for the corresponding depth intervals. Due to the high velocities of the P-waves, the short distances examined and the weak character of most of the waveforms in the dataset, the results included several unrealistically high or low V_p values, many of which were removed as outliers using a two-step interquartile outlier removal approach. The outliers for the V_p computation were in the range of 7-33% of the initial number of data points, which is considered rather small considering the previously mentioned difficulties in measuring V_p . Based on the final data points, we computed the mean $V_p \pm 1$ s.d. for each depth interval examined and we provided a V_p velocity model for the site of the CORSSA infrastructure. We used our V_p values and the V_s values of Roumelioti et al. (2018) to compute V_p/V_s ratios for the different depth intervals examined, but also to demonstrate that continuous monitoring of this quantity is feasible with the applied method.

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